

Studies on the Thermal Degradation of Cellobiose**

CHANDER KALA, I. S. GUR, H. L. BHATNAGAR*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

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Kinetics of pyrolysis of cellobiose as a model compound of cellulose has been studied by isothermal thermogravimetry. The thermal degradation was carried out at twelve temperatures in the range 491 to 536 °K. The energy of activation was calculated by two independent methods, i.e., by Avrami-Erofeev equation and Jacobs-Kureishy method, and its value comes out to be 26.89 kcal/mole with a frequency factor $2.31 \times 10^9 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. The entropy of activation has been found to be -21.34 e.u. and the free energy of activation 37.84 kcal/mole. These values have been calculated at 513 °K, the transition temperature for cellobiose as observed in DTA studies. A possible mechanism for the thermal degradation of cellobiose has been suggested.

STUDIES on the kinetics of thermal degradation of cellulose, its derivatives, and cellulose treated with different formulations to impart flame proofing have been made by various investigators¹⁻⁶. This is important due to the wide use of cellulose in both civil and military spheres.

Although some investigations have been carried out on the chemical degradation of cellobiose in the presence of acids and bases, not much attention has been paid so far to its behaviour in the presence of high temperatures. Lorant and Boros⁷ had studied the weight changes (H_2O release) of cellobiose and other carbohydrates over a wide range of temperature and observed that these were not significantly changed by ordinary cooking temperatures except that there may be a small amount of anhydride formation on the surface. Kato⁸ pyrolysed cellobiose, cellulose, and other carbohydrates and volatile products were detected by gas chromatography. The same kind of work had been done by Gardiner⁹. Heyns and Klier¹⁰ have reported that cellulose, cellobiose and a number of other carbohydrates give the same volatile products on thermal degradation. Puddington¹¹ studied the thermal decomposition of cellobiose in vacuum and had reported the various products of the degradation along with the energy of activation for the process.

In the present studies cellobiose has been taken as a model compound for cellulose and the kinetics of its thermal degradation using the isothermal thermogravimetry has been studied with a view to elucidating the mechanism of the thermal degradation of the latter.

Experimental

Cellobiose was washed thoroughly first with benzene and then with acetone and vacuum dried to constant weight.

The apparatus used for carrying out pyrolysis of the sample at constant temperature is shown in Fig. 1. A quartz spring balance (A) was used for noting the weight of the sample continuously. The quartz spring having a capacity of 500 mg was suspended from the hook (B) joined to glass tube

Fig. 1. (diagram of the pyrolysis apparatus)

A. Quartz spring balance; B. Hook for balance; C. Glass tube in which thermocouple was seated; D. B-40 joint cone in which tubes C & J were sealed; E. Pt. crucible; F. Horizontal pointer of the crucible; G. Outer jacket; H. B-14 joint; I. one way stop cock; J. Tube for introducing the sample; K. B-14 joint sealed in cone D.

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(C) which was sealed into cone (D) of a B-40 joint. A platinum crucible (E) was hung from the lower end of the spring for supporting the sample. A horizontal pointer (F), fixed to the hook of the crucible, was used for the purpose of measuring the extension of the spring by a cathetometer. The spring was calibrated by measuring its extension corresponding to different standard weights and plotting a graph between weight and extension which was found to be linear. The weight of a sample could therefore be measured continuously from the graph by noting the extension.

A special arrangement was made for introducing the sample after the temperature inside the jacket (G) had become constant and a vacuum of 10^{-3} mm was obtained. The sample was initially put between the stopper (H) and stop-cock (I) in the form of small granules. The length of glass tube (J) was so adjusted that its lower end, bent at an appropriate angle, could be placed over the platinum crucible by giving it rotation about the B-14 joint (K). The stop-cock (I) was opened partially so that no part of the sample went-down. The furnace was slipped over jacket (G) which was then evacuated. The temperature was read with the help of a Pt-Rh thermocouple introduced through the tube (C) and sealed at the lower end. When the temperature had become constant and the vacuum was maximum (10^{-3} mm), the sample was introduced into the platinum crucible by opening the stop-cock (I) fully and then closing it. The stop-watch was started simultaneously. The bent end of the glass tube (J) was moved away from the spring by rotating it through a required angle. This technique of introducing the sample was devised to minimise the heating time of the sample and to avoid decomposition during the period it required to attain a constant temperature. The temperature remained constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ$

The height of the pointer (F) was measured with the help of a cathetometer before and immediately after introducing the sample. The difference between these readings gave the weight of the sample. The weight at different time intervals was measured in a similar manner. The weight of the sample introduced in each case was between 50 and 70 mg.

The thermal degradation was carried out at twelve temperatures in the range 491 to 536°K. The range was determined by the peaks observed in the DTA studies.

Results and Discussion

The weight versus time curves at different temperatures are represented in Figs. 2 and 3. In some cases where the reading could be taken immediately after introducing the sample, particularly at lower temperatures, initially there was a small but rapid loss of the sample weight followed by a major weight

Fig. 2. Plots of weight vs time for pure cellobiose powder

Fig. 3. Plots of weight vs time for pure cellobiose powder

loss. In other cases, where the reading could not be taken immediately, the portion of the curve showing rapid loss of a small weight is not very apparent. The rate of major weight loss started

decreasing after some time and ultimately the weight became constant. The average weight loss was about 75.5 per cent.

The initial rapid loss of small weight is attributed to the loss of sorbed moisture and was neglected. For calculating the degree of degradation, initial weight was considered to be the weight at the point of inflection between the initial weight loss and the final major weight loss and the corresponding time was taken as the zero time.

Evaluation of Kinetic Parameters :

The degree of degradation was calculated by using the equation

$$\alpha = \frac{W_i - W_t}{W_i - W_f} \quad \dots (1)$$

where W_i is the initial weight of the sample, W_f is its final weight and W_t is its weight at any time 't' of degradation.

The data so obtained were found to fit the Avarami-Erofeev equation

$$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2} = k't. \quad \dots (2)$$

This is evident from the linear plots of $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$ against time as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The values of k' were calculated from the slopes of these graphs and are given alongwith corresponding temperatures in Table 1.

The energy of activation, ΔE , and the frequency factor, A , were determined by using the Arrhenius equation

$$k' = Ae^{-\Delta E/RT} \quad \dots (3)$$

The plot of $\ln k'$ versus T^{-1} is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 4. Plots of $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$ vs time for pure cellobiose powder

Fig. 5. Plots of $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$ vs time for pure cellobiose powder

TABLE 1—PURE CELLOBIOSE—SAMPLE NO. I

Temperature °K	1/T × 10 ³ (°K)	k'/sec. × 10 ⁴	ln k'
491.0	2.0345	2.628	-8.2441
495.0	2.02	3.198	-8.0478
498.0	2.0075	3.786	-8.8790
501.0	1.996	4.080	-7.8042
505.0	1.980	5.276	-7.5471
511.0	1.9569	7.191	-7.2375
514.5	1.9486	8.666	-7.0509
522.5	1.9188	12.720	-6.6671
526.0	1.9011	14.920	-6.5076
527.0	1.8975	15.870	-6.4459
528.5	1.8921	17.000	-6.9771
536.0	1.866	26.830	-5.9396

$$\begin{aligned} \sum 1/T \times 10^3 &= 23.4090 & \sum \ln k' &= -85.7479 \\ \sum 1/T^2 \times 10^6 &= 45.7000 & \sum \ln k' \cdot 1/T \times 10^3 &= -167.7451 \end{aligned}$$

Using the method of least squares,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E &= 26.89 \text{ kcal/mole,} \\ A &= 2.31 \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 6. Plots of $\ln k'$ vs $1/T$ for pure cellobiose powder

The energy of activation was also calculated by Jacobs and Kureishy's^{1,2} method according to which, at a given temperature,

$$F(\alpha_{n+1}) - F(\alpha_n) = k'_1(t_{n+1} - t_n) \quad \dots (4)$$

where α_{n+1} and α_n are the degrees of degradation at times t_{n+1} and t_n respectively and $F(\alpha)$ is a function of the degree of degradation.

If the same experiment is repeated at a different temperature, then for the same values of α , equation (4) becomes

$$F(\alpha_{n+1}) - F(\alpha_n) = k'_2(t'_{n+1} - t'_n) \quad \dots (4a)$$

By combining equations (4) and (4a) with the Arrhenius equation it can be shown that the plot of $\log(t_{n+1} - t_n)$ against T^{-1} is linear with a slope $\Delta E/2.303R$.

The value of the energy of activation obtained by this method was in agreement with that by Avarami-Erofeev equation.

Since the plot of weight versus time is linear for most portion of thermal degradation, the order of the reaction was assumed to be zero. However, the order of the reaction in the later stages of degradation changes as is obvious from Figs. 2 and 3. For a zero order reaction the enthalpy of activation, ΔH , is equal to the energy of activation, ΔE . It can be shown by the theory of absolute reaction rate that

$$A = \frac{kT}{h} e^{\Delta S/R} \quad \dots (5)$$

where ΔS is the entropy of activation for the process. The free energy of activation is given by

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad \dots (6)$$

The energy of activation for the thermal degradation of cellobiose is found to be 26.89 kcal/mole and the frequency factor, A , has a value $2.31 \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. The free energy of activation is 37.84 kcal/mole and the entropy of activation -21.34 e.u. The values of ΔS and ΔG have been calculated at 513°K, the transition temperature for cellobiose as observed in DTA studies^{1,3}.

Thermal decomposition of cellobiose in vacuum had been studied by Puddington^{1,1} who determined the progress of the reaction by collecting the reaction products (H_2O , CO_2 and CO) and measuring their amounts after separating them. According to these studies cellobiose at high temperatures decomposed in two steps with elimination of two moles of water/mole of sugar, followed by the loss of CO_2 and CO . Other products of degradation were not analysed. Activation energies were calculated from the slopes of the straight lines obtained when the logarithms of the times required to reach various percentages of the products were plotted against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature of reaction. An overall energy of activation of 60 kcal/mole suddenly decreased to about 40 kcal/mole after the cellobiose had lost about 10% water.

The values of energy of activation reported by Puddington^{1,1} are much higher than the values obtained in the present studies. In order to verify the correctness of results, the energy of activation was calculated by two different methods, i.e., by using Avarami-Erofeev equation and Kureishy's method. Since both the methods give the same values of ΔE , therefore 26.89 kcal/mole can be taken to be the authentic value of the energy of activation for the thermal degradation of cellobiose.

Mechanism :

It has been reported by Puddington^{1,1} that in the initial stages of thermal degradation of cellobiose

water is the only volatile product. The overall thermal decomposition is also mainly a dehydration reaction because of the large amount of water produced as compared to CO_2 and CO . Formic acid and some other volatile and solid substances, which could not be characterized by Puddington, were also produced during the pyrolysis of cellobiose. In the present case, the decomposition proceeds as a reaction of zero order for maximum portion in the temperature range $491\text{--}536^\circ\text{K}$ and the energy of activation remains constant. This suggests that the mechanism of thermal degradation over this range of temperature is the same as reported.

It is suggested that initially cellobiose loses a molecule of water and gives another solid. The solid may be levoglucosan, which has been reported^{1,4} as a product of thermal degradation of many sugars. Levoglucosan then decomposes further to give H_2O , CO_2 , CO and formic acid along with other volatile and non-volatile products. The formation of a polymer^{11,15} might have taken place in the later stages of pyrolysis when the order of reaction changes.

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